

The excess mortality is strongly underestimated

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Abstract

This article show how excess mortality by the CBS possibly is underestimated.

We correct the expected mortality with the estimated number of people who died in earlier years than expected because of the pandemic. For 2021 this correction is 8K. Then the excess mortality increases from 16K (CBS) to 24K.

There also are people who died by covid in, say, April, who without the pandemic would have died later in the same year, say October. With this effect total excess mortality rises with 6K to 30K.

Excess mortality is divided in covid and non-covid. De large increase in non-covid deaths is striking.

The analysis supports the conjecture that excess mortality is underestimated.

Note: This is the short version. The full version has more backgrounds and explanations.

1 Introduction

Note: The numbers in this article are for the Netherlands. For you own country use the appropriate numbers.

With the pandemic excess mortality has become a matter of interest. The main starting point is that there must be concurrence on the numbers. This is not always the case. I give some examples with the numbers from the CBS (Dutch Central Bureau of Statistics). I use estimates in those calculations.

At the end conclusions and recommendations.

In my main article I elaborate more on estimates, manner of calculation etcetera (Lugtigheid, 2023d).

2 Excess mortality and expected mortality

Excess mortality per year is actual mortality minus expected mortality.

Many older people who died in 2020 from covid would have died in 2021 without the pandemic. Their number can be estimated at January first of 2021. Hence we have to lower the expected mortality for 2021 by that number. And so on for subsequent years.

A person dies from covid in, say, April. Without the pandemic that person would have died in, say, October. Then for the whole year this death does not count as excess mortality in the usual definition. This I call excess mortality within the year.

3 Mortality in 2020

In 2019 the CBS estimated the expected mortality for 2020 at 153.402 (CBS, 2019). In 2020 year 168.678 people died (CBS, n.d.-b). This was 15 thousand more than expected.

In 2020 20.661, rounded 21 thousand, people died from covid (CBS, 2022). I estimate that without the pandemic seven thousand of those also would have died in 2020. This is excess mortality in the year. Then the annual year on year excess mortality from covid in 2020 is 14 thousand. With excess mortality of 15 thousand excess mortality from other causes in 2020 is one thousand.

Suppose one thousand people have died from other causes earlier in the year than expected. This could pertain to older people who where not allowed to have visitors and therefore suffered psychological harm and died earlier. Then the total excess mortality in 2020 becomes 23 thousand (15+7+1). See table 1.

Table 1: Total excess mortality 2020

Mortality	Covid	Non-Covid	Total
Excess mortality op jaarbasis	14.000	1.000	15.000
<u>Excess mortality in same year</u>	<u>7.000</u>	<u>1.000</u>	<u>8.000</u>
Total Excess mortality 2020	21.000	2.000	23.000

4 Mortality in 2021

In 2019 the CBS estimates the mortality for 2021 to be 155.232. (CBS, 2019). In 2020 the CBS adjusted this to 154.887 (CBS, 2023a).

In 2020 21 thousand people died from covid. I estimate that from these eight thousand people (table 3: estimate I) would have died in 2021 without the pandemic. I decrease the expected mortality of 154.887 with eight thousand to 146.887 thousand. I round these numbers.

I assume one disturbing factor – covid. Then the estimates should be around equal. A possible explanation for the difference is the following. The expected mortality is recalculated with a historically based percentage. This percentage is volume related. However covid hits the weak the hardest. Then the distribution of the people in the remaining group changes. And then the percentage for recalculation has to be adjusted accordingly. See for more Lugtigheid, 2023a.

In 2021 19 thousand people died from covid (CBS, 2022). I estimate that from these five thousand people would have died also in 2021 without covid. Then the excess mortality due to covid is 14 thousand. The excess mortality by other causes than covid becomes two thousand and ten thousand. See table 2 for an overview.

Table 2: Excess mortality 2021

	CBS	Ajusted
Expected mortality (2019)	155.232	155.232
Correction	345	
<u>Deceased in 2020</u>	—	<u>8.000</u>
Expected mortality	154.887	147.232
Expected mortality (rounded)	155.000	147.000
Actual mortality (CBS)	171.000	171.000
<u>Expected mortality (rounded)</u>	<u>155.000</u>	<u>147.000</u>
Excess mortality	16.000	24.000
Excess mortality	16.000	24.000
<u>Excess mortality by covid</u>	<u>14.000</u>	<u>14.000</u>
Excess mortality by non-covid	2.000	10.000

In 2021 the adjusted excess mortality on an annual base was 24 thousand.

I estimate that in 2021 five thousand people died early by covid who, without the pandemic, would have died later in the year. This is excess mortality in the year. There were also people who died early by other causes than covid but would otherwise have died later that year. This might for example be because of postponed medical treatment. How many is difficult to estimate. For this paper I assume their number to be one thousand. Then the total excess mortality in 2021 equals 30 thousand people (24+5+1). Or, otherwise calculated, 19 thousand people died prematurely from covid and eleven thousand from other causes. See table 3.

Table 3: Excess mortality 2021

Mortality	Covid	Non-Covid	Total
Excess mortality year on year	14.000	10.000	24.000
<u>Excess mortality in same year</u>	<u>5.000</u>	<u>1.000</u>	<u>6.000</u>
Excess mortality 2021	19.000	11.000	30.000

Calculations like these can and must be made for 2022 and later years.

5 Conclusion

When we consider the above effects we see that total excess mortality in 2021 gets much higher than with the CBS. This gives a better view of the damage done by covid.

The strong increase of mortality from non-covid is striking.

It is recommended to develop methods to better estimate the relevant quantities.

Literature

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